

Progress and Prospects of China's Atmospheric Environmental Management Policies

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Abstract

This study aims to comprehensively analyze the evolution and effectiveness of China's atmospheric environmental management policies, providing a scientific basis for subsequent policy optimization. Through literature research, relevant domestic theories and research findings are systematically sorted out, and an in-depth analysis is conducted on the implementation background, specific measures, and implementation effects of regulatory, regulatory plus market-based policies, and collaborative governance. The study finds that China has achieved significant results in air quality improvement and pollutant emission control, but still faces challenges such as insufficient policy flexibility and coordination difficulties among stakeholders. In the future, policy combinations should be further optimized, research on collaborative strategies for new pollutant control and climate change response should be strengthened, and international cooperation should be actively participated in to learn from international advanced experiences, thereby promoting the continuous improvement of atmospheric environmental management policies.

Keywords: *Atmospheric environment management policy; Regulatory policy; Market - based policy; Collaborative governance.*

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Introduction

As a crucial component of the ecosystem, the atmospheric environment plays an irreplaceable key role in human health, ecological balance, and economic development. China's atmospheric environment management policies have evolved from single-pollutant control to multi-pollutant coordinated governance, and from local governance to regional joint prevention and control. Since the 21st century, with the rapid advancement of industrialization and

urbanization in China, regional compound air pollution characterized by PM_{2.5} and O₃ has become increasingly prominent. The high societal attention to haze issues has driven the transformation of air pollution control mode from pollutant emission concentration control to environmental quality improvement as the core (Song et al., 2021). However, China's atmospheric environment still faces multiple challenges including unreasonable industrial structure, insufficient energy structure optimization, and lagging transportation

structure adjustment (Wang et al., 2022). Against this background, this paper, from the perspective of policy portfolio optimization, comprehensively employs literature research and case analysis methods to explore the integration paths of regulatory, market-based, and collaborative governance policies. It aims to enrich and improve the research framework of atmospheric environmental management policies, providing new perspectives and methodological support for academic discussions in related fields (Song, 2020; Zhu et al., 2021). At the practical level, this study aims to extract successful experiences and identify existing problems through sorting out and evaluating existing policies, proposing future research directions and development strategies for atmospheric environmental management policies. The study intends to provide valuable reference for both academic research and policy practice in relevant fields.

Research Progress on Atmospheric Environmental Management Policy at Home and Abroad

In recent years, scholars at home and abroad have carried out extensive research on atmospheric environment management policies and formed rich academic achievements. In terms of domestic research, scholars pay attention to the process of air pollution control in China and the evolution of its policies. For example, Xue et al. (2021) systematically reviewed the characteristics of China's atmospheric environment management in the past 50 years, pointing out the policy transformation path from concentration control to total control to quality improvement. Based on the environmental Kuznets curve, Li et al. (2021) discussed the relationship between economic growth and air quality in key areas of air pollution prevention and control such as Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei, the Yangtze River Delta and the Pearl River Delta, and found that the implementation of the policy significantly promoted the improvement of regional environmental quality. Jin (2024) focused on the third "Atmospheric Ten" policy goals and implementation paths, emphasizing the importance of PM_{2.5} concentration control and

the key role of regional joint prevention and control mechanism. In terms of international research, the experience of atmospheric environment management in Europe and the United States has provided an important reference for China. For example, the Clean Air Act of the United States has successfully solved the problems of acid rain and the destruction of the ozone layer through the introduction of market mechanisms and strict law enforcement; the European Union has achieved the overall improvement of air quality in the region through cross-border collaboration and unified standards (Cai, 2020). Generally speaking, domestic and foreign studies have shown that scientific and reasonable policy design and effective implementation are the key to improving the quality of the atmospheric environment.

The Development of Regulatory Environmental Policy

Early Regulatory Policy Initiatives

The regulatory policy in early atmospheric environment management mainly focused on the formulation of emission standards and the control of total pollutants. Its implementation background is closely related to China's high dependence on fossil energy such as coal in the industrialization process. Since the 1970s, with the rapid progress of industrialization, soot pollution has become the main feature of China's atmospheric environment. During this period, the environmental policy has gradually changed from scratch and formed a preliminary framework guided by concentration control (Xue et al., 2021). As an important part of the early regulatory policy, the formulation of emission standards requires industrial enterprises to comply with relevant regulations by setting pollutant emission limits, so as to reduce the emission of sulfur dioxide, soot and other major pollutants. In 1973, the Trial Implementation Standards for Industrial "Three Wastes" Emissions was first released, marking the beginning of China's atmospheric pollutant emission management. During the Ninth Five-Year Plan, the country began to implement the control system for the total emission of major pollutants, and included sulfur dioxide and soot in the key control objects, which laid the

foundation for the deepening of China's subsequent atmospheric environment management policy (Xue et al., 2021).

Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Policy Implementation

Early control policies have achieved remarkable results in improving the quality of the atmospheric environment and controlling the emission of pollutants, especially in the pollution control of specific regions and industries. Taking sulfur dioxide emissions as an example, through the formulation of strict emission standards and total control measures, the national sulfur dioxide emissions showed a gradual downward trend during the period from the Ninth Five-Year Plan to the Tenth Five-Year Plan period, and the air quality in some key industrial cities has been significantly improved (Song et al., 2021). In addition, the effective implementation of early control policies has also promoted the technological reform of enterprises and the popularization of pollution control facilities. For example, in the thermal power generation industry, the installation rate of desulfurization devices increased from less than 10% at the end of the 20th century to more than 80% in 2010, greatly reducing the emission intensity of sulfur dioxide (Zhu et al., 2021).

Limitations of Existence

Although early regulatory policies have played an important role in improving the quality of the atmospheric environment, there are problems such as high implementation costs, insufficient enterprise motivation and poor policy flexibility. First of all, the implementation of regulatory policies often requires a large amount of investment in the construction, operation and maintenance of pollution control facilities, which puts forward high requirements for the economic affordability of local governments and enterprises. In some economically underdeveloped areas, due to the lack of adequate financial support, it is difficult for some enterprises to complete pollution control tasks on time, which greatly reduces the effectiveness of policy implementation. Secondly, early regulatory policies are mainly executive orders, and the lack of design of incentive mechanisms for enterprises makes enterprises lack internal

motivation to fulfill their environmental protection responsibilities. Especially in some small and medium-sized enterprises, due to the high cost of compliance and the lack of obvious benefits, some enterprises choose to evade regulation or steal, which weakens the practical effect of the policy (Huang et al., 2024). In addition, regulatory policies are less flexible and difficult to adapt to the differentiated needs of different regions and industries (Li et al., 2024). For example, uniform emission standards may be too loose in some regions, while in others, they are too strict.

Regulatory and Market-Based Policy Combination Model

Application of Market Mechanism in Atmospheric Environmental Management

The application of market mechanism in atmospheric environmental management is mainly reflected in the introduction and implementation of policy tools such as emissions trading and environmental taxes. The mechanism of sewage trading can not only encourage enterprises to actively reduce pollutant emissions to save quotas, but also optimize resource allocation through market supply and demand, so as to improve the efficiency of environmental governance (Yu et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2023). At the same time, environmental tax, as another important market-oriented policy tool, guides enterprises to choose cleaner production methods by taxing pollution behavior and internalizing external costs (Wang et al., 2021). These two market mechanisms complement each other, which compensates for the lack of flexibility and efficiency through economic incentives, and traditional regulatory policies that provide the necessary binding framework for market mechanisms through mandatory standards.

In addition, the application of market mechanisms also reflects the shift in the role of the government in environmental governance, that is, the gradual transition from a single command controller to a rule maker and a market guide. For example, in the emission trading system, the government is responsible for setting overall emission targets and allocation

rules, while specific emission reductions are determined by the market (Su et al., 2016). This model not only reduces the administrative burden on the government, but also enhances the enthusiasm of enterprises to participate in environmental governance.

The Practical Case of the Combination Mode

The combination of market mechanism and regulatory policies is not only a technological innovation, but also a profound change in governance concepts. Taking China's Yangtze River Delta region as an example, the region has actively explored the combination of regulatory and market-oriented policies in atmospheric environmental management, and has achieved remarkable results. After the State Council issued the Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Air Pollution in 2013, the Yangtze River Delta region established a joint prevention and control mechanism, and piloted the trading system for pollutant discharge rights (Zhu et al., 2021; Wang., 2020). Specifically, local governments first clarify the emission reduction responsibilities of enterprises in the region by setting strict emission standards and total control targets; second, they allow enterprises to flexibly adjust their emission reduction strategies by purchasing or selling emission quotas on the basis of meeting basic emission reduction requirements. This two-track policy design not only ensures the rigid constraints of environmental governance, but also provides more operating space for enterprises.

The Advantages and Challenges of the Combination Model

The advantages of the regulatory and market-oriented policy combination model in atmospheric environment management are mainly reflected in the three aspects of policy flexibility, efficiency improvement and multi-party participation. First of all, the introduction of the market mechanism makes policy implementation more flexible. Enterprises can choose the most economical way to reduce emissions according to their own actual situation, so as to reduce the overall cost of governance (Wang et al., 2022). Secondly, through the adjustment of the market supply and

demand relationship, the allocation of resources can be optimized, and the efficiency of policy implementation is significantly improved. For example, the emission rights trading mechanism can encourage enterprises with low emission reduction costs to undertake more emission reduction tasks, so as to minimize the emission reduction costs of the whole society (Ye et al., 2016).

However, the model also faces many challenges in policy design and regulation. First of all, policy design needs to take into account the rigidity of regulatory policies and the flexibility of market mechanisms, which puts forward high requirements for the professional ability and comprehensive coordination ability of policymakers. Secondly, the effective operation of the market mechanism depends on a perfect legal framework and a transparent information sharing mechanism, and the lack of these conditions may lead to market failure or policy implementation deviation. For example, there may be problems such as unfair quota allocation and transaction price distortion in the emission rights trading market, which will affect the policy effect (Cao et al., 2023). Finally, the complexity of cross-regional collaborative governance has also increased the difficulty of supervision. How to achieve policy coordination and resource integration between regions is still an urgent problem to be solved.

The Embodiment of Collaborative Governance in Atmospheric Environmental Management

Experience of Cross-Regional Collaborative Governance

Collaborative governance of atmospheric environment emphasizes the joint participation of multiple subjects, and the government, enterprises and the public play different roles and assume corresponding responsibilities in this process. Cross-regional coordinated management of the atmospheric environment is a key measure to deal with regional air pollution problems, and its successful cases have provided valuable experience for other regions of China. Take Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei and the Yangtze River Delta regions as examples, these two

regions have established relatively perfect cooperation mechanisms in the coordinated control of air pollution. In terms of organizational structure, the Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region has set up a special working group led by the central government to coordinate the governance actions of all provinces and cities in the region; while the Yangtze River Delta region has built a multi-level collaborative governance framework through cooperation agreements between three provinces and one municipal government (Suo, 2020; Sun et al., 2022). In terms of cooperation mechanism, both places pay attention to the establishment of a normalized joint meeting system, regularly discuss governance plans and evaluate policy effects. In addition, the construction of an information sharing platform is also one of the important experiences of cross-regional collaborative governance. For example, the Yangtze River Delta region has realized the real-time interoperability of air quality information in various cities in the region by building an air quality monitoring data sharing platform, thus providing a scientific basis for joint prevention and control (Wang, 2020). These successful experiences show that cross-regional collaborative governance needs to rely on strong organizational guarantees, efficient cooperation mechanisms and a perfect information sharing system to effectively respond to the challenges of regional air pollution.

Challenges for Collaborative Governance

First of all, the difficulty of coordination between subjects is an important factor restricting the effectiveness of collaborative governance. Due to the differences between the government, enterprises and the public in interests and action logic, it is easy to disagree or even conflict in the process of policy implementation (Hu et al., 2022). Secondly, the uneven distribution of benefits exacerbates the complexity of collaborative governance. There are differences in the level of economic development and resource endowment in different regions, which makes it difficult to achieve a fair distribution of benefits in cross-regional collaborative governance. Economically underdeveloped areas may face development pressure due to more governance

responsibilities, which will affect their enthusiasm for participation (Meng et al., 2018). Finally, the difficulty of supervision is also a major problem facing collaborative governance. Due to the cross-border transmission characteristics of air pollution, regulatory measures in a single region are often difficult to work, and cross-regional joint supervision faces problems such as inconsistent law enforcement standards and information asymmetry (Liu et al., 2020). In response to the above challenges, we should further improve the collaborative governance mechanism in the future, and gradually solve the bottleneck in collaborative governance by strengthening the top-level design, optimizing the benefit distribution scheme, and improving the level of supervision technology.

Progress of China 's Atmospheric Environmental Management Policy

It is reported that in 2024, of the 339 cities at the prefecture level and above (hereinafter referred to as 339 cities), 222 cities met the ambient air quality standard, accounting for 65.5%, an increase of 19 cities over 2023. Overall, the air quality in the country is stable and good, the heavily polluted weather has been significantly reduced, and the concentration of major pollutants shows a continuous downward trend. The average concentration of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) in cities at the prefecture level and above reached 29.3 ug/m³, down 2.7% from 2023; the proportion of days with excellent air quality was 87.2%, an increase of 1.7 percentage points over 2023; and the proportion of heavily polluted days was 0.9%, a decrease of 0.7 percentage points compared with 2023 (State of the Environment Bulletin of China).. In addition, the concentrations of PM₁₀ and sulfur dioxide (SO₂) have also decreased significantly. Among them, the concentration of SO₂ has been effectively controlled nationwide under the promotion of a series of emission capping policies since the Tenth Five-Year Plan, and the problem of acid rain has been basically solved (Song et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2021).

From the perspective of many dimensions such as pollutant emission control, industrial structure optimization and energy structure adjustment,

China's atmospheric environment management policy has achieved comprehensive and far-reaching results. First of all, in terms of pollutant emission control, the implementation of programmatic documents such as "Ten Atmospheric" and "Three-Year Action Plan to Win the Blue Sky Defense War" has significantly reduced the emissions of major air pollutants and their nitrogen oxides (NO_x) and volatile organic VOCs) (Li et al., 2024). Through the comprehensive control of multiple pollution sources and the coordinated emission reduction strategy of multiple pollutants, the continuous improvement of air quality has been comprehensively promoted, laying a solid foundation for regional compound pollution prevention and control (Wang et al., 2020). Secondly, in terms of industrial structure optimization, the measures to reduce production and carbon in high-energy-consuming industries under the guidance of policies have achieved remarkable results. The energy-saving and consumption-reducing indicators of key industries such as steel and cement have gradually increased, which has promoted the green transformation of the industrial structure (Wang et al., 2020; Song et al., 2016). According to relevant research, from 2016 to 2018, the coordination of pollution reduction-carbon reduction-economic indicators in many provinces in China has been improved, and the binary coupling coordination in some regions has reached the level of high-quality and coordinated development (Wang et al., 2022; Luo et al., 2024). Finally, in terms of energy structural adjustment, the proportion of non-fossil energy has become an important highlight of policy implementation. Data shows that during the 14th Five-Year Plan period, the proportion of non-fossil energy in primary energy in China increased at a rate of about 1% per year, and breakthroughs have been made in the scale and cost control of renewable energy power generation (Wang et al., 2020).

Conclusions and Future Prospect of China's Atmospheric Environmental Management Policy

Although fruitful results have been achieved in the field of atmospheric environmental

management policy research at home and abroad, there are still some urgent problems and research gaps that need to be solved. First of all, in terms of the combination of regulatory and market-based policies, the existing research focuses on the impact assessment of a single policy tool, and there is a lack of in-depth discussion of the synergies between the two (Wang et al., 2022). Secondly, in the field of collaborative governance, although the literature has analyzed the role positioning of the government, enterprises and the public, there is still a lack of systematic research on how to achieve efficient cooperation between multiple subjects (Song et al., 2021; Wu et al., 2025). In addition, the research on the treatment of new pollutants and the coordinated response to climate change and air pollution is still in its infancy, and more theoretical exploration and practical verification are urgently needed.

Policy Portfolio Optimization Direction

Based on the existing policy foundation and development trend, the future optimization of China's atmospheric environmental management policy should focus on the organic combination of regulatory, market-oriented and collaborative governance policies to improve the overall efficiency of policies (Zhang et al., 2025). Regulatory policies have mandatory advantages in pollutant emission control and environmental standard setting, but the problems of high implementation costs and insufficient flexibility need to be solved urgently (Zhang et al., 2025). To this end, the policy can be more adaptable and targeted by introducing a dynamic adjustment mechanism. For example, in the formulation of emission standards, differentiated management and control strategies are implemented in combination with the level of regional economic development and the characteristics of industrial structure, so as to balance the relationship between environmental protection and economic development. At the same time, the application of market-oriented policies such as pollutant rights transactions and environmental taxes needs to be further expanded and the mechanism design needs to be improved (Kong et al., 2025). In addition, as a supplementary means, collaborative governance should be further strengthened in the policy

framework to ensure the sharing of interests and responsibilities among various subjects (Wang et al., 2024).

Improve the Supervision System

First of all, strengthen the construction of the supervision team. The professional quality of the atmospheric environment supervision team directly determines the effect of policy implementation, so the construction of the supervision team must be strengthened. First of all, the professional ability of supervisors should be improved through regular training, assessment and certification to ensure that they master the latest laws, regulations and technical standards. Secondly, in view of the scattered and complex situation of pollution sources, it is necessary to appropriately increase the number of supervisors, especially in key pollution areas and industries, to achieve full coverage of pollution sources (Hu, 2021). In addition, the introduction of third-party professional institutions to participate in supervision is also an effective supplementary means, which can make up for the shortcomings of existing regulatory forces and improve the scientificity and fairness of supervision.

Secondly, innovate regulatory means. The rapid development of modern information technology has provided new tools and means for atmospheric environmental supervision. Big data analysis technology can integrate data from different monitoring sites, identify the distribution law of pollution sources and the trend of pollution diffusion, so as to provide decision-making support for accurate pollution control (Sun et al., 2023). Artificial intelligence technology can be applied to the optimization of real-time monitoring systems to realize automatic warning of abnormal emission behavior through rapid processing and analysis of massive data. In addition, the application of blockchain technology can improve the transparency and credibility of environmental monitoring data and prevent data falsified. By building a blockchain-based data sharing platform, information circulation between different departments will be more efficient, thus improving the overall supervision efficiency.

Third, establish a public supervision mechanism. Establishing a public supervision mechanism is an important means to ensure the effective implementation of atmospheric environment management policies. First of all, a convenient reporting platform should be set up to encourage the public to report illegal emissions, and give appropriate rewards and protection to whistleblowers (Li et al., 2022). Secondly, carry out public satisfaction surveys, regularly evaluate the effectiveness of policy implementation, and adjust policies and measures in a timely manner according to feedback. In addition, the disclosure of key information in the process of policy implementation, such as pollutant emission data, regulatory penalty results, etc., can enhance the transparency of policies and enable the public to better understand and support relevant policies. Through the above measures, the public will become an important participant in the governance of the atmospheric environment and jointly promote the continuous improvement of air quality.

Strategies to Deal with New Atmospheric Environmental Problems

In the future, China's atmospheric environment management needs to formulate more forward-looking policies and strategies for the treatment of new pollutants and the coordinated response to climate change and air pollution. On the one hand, the emergence of new pollutants challenges the traditional treatment model, such as the compound pollution of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) (Li et al., 2025). In view of such problems, we should strengthen source control, promote the upgrading of industrial structure, reduce the proportion of high-polluting industries, and increase support for the research and development of clean energy technology to promote green technology innovation. On the other hand, there is a significant synergy between climate change and air pollution, so greenhouse gas emission reduction and air pollutant control need to be considered under the same policy framework (Dong et al., 2021). Specifically, the integrated management of the two types of pollutants can be realized by implementing the linkage mechanism between the trading of carbon emission rights and the trading of

emission rights. In addition, with the advancement of the Belt and Road Initiative, China also needs to strengthen cooperation with countries along the route in the field of air pollution prevention and control, jointly respond to the problem of cross-border air pollution, and build a regional environmental management network (Wu, 2023; Jiang et al., 2025). By strengthening international cooperation and introducing advanced technology and management experience, we will contribute to the construction of a community with a shared future for mankind.

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References

- Cai, F. (2020). Review and prospect on the atmospheric pollution control in China. *Environment and Sustainable Development*, 45(3), 5-15. <https://doi.org/10.19758/j.cnki.issn1673-288x.202003005>
- Cao, P., & Liu, C. (2023). Does emission trading promote high-quality economic development? Evidence from prefecture-level and above cities in China. *Journal of Management Sciences in China*, 26(6), 39-56. <https://doi.org/10.19920/j.cnki.jmsc.2023.06.003>
- Dong, Z., Zhou, J., Bi, F., Song, Y., Zhang, Z., Peng, C., & Zhao, Y. (2021). Research on synergistic policy of climate change and ecological environment protection. *Chinese Journal of Environmental Management*, 13(1), 25-34. <https://doi.org/10.16868/j.cnki.1674-6252.2021.01.025>
- Huang, X., & Liu, Y. (2024). Precise or off-target: Research on the suitability of policy tools and policy objectives — Fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis based on atmospheric environmental regulation policy. *Social Science Research*, (03), 49-59. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1000-4769.2024.03.005>
- Hu, G., Zong, J., & Gan, R. (2022). Local environmental competition and regional collaborative governance model under the central environmental supervision. *The Journal of Humanities*, (02), 50-60. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.0447-662X.2022.02.006>
- Hu, S. (2021). Analysis on the change of atmospheric environmental management focus. *China Resources Comprehensive Utilization*, 39(8), 130-132. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1008-9500.2021.08.036>
- Jiang, B., Feng, J., Gao, J., Gao, Y., & Zhang, H. (2025). Achievements, challenges and countermeasures of the implementation of the Green “Belt and Road” strategy. *Journal of Environmental Engineering Technology*, 1-12.
- Jin, J. (2024). The third “Ten Atmosphere” focuses on PM2.5. *Ecological Economy*, 40(2), 9-12.
- Kong, S., & He, M. (2025). Analysis of the influence and mechanisms of the ‘Blue Sky Defense War’ on the synergistic effects of CO₂-PM2.5-O₃ emission reduction. *Research of Environmental Sciences*, 1-19. <https://doi.org/10.13198/j.issn.1001-6929.2025.06.07>
- Li, J. (2020). “Dilemma of collaborative action” and its solutions in regional governance: Taking collaborative governance of air pollution in Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei region as an example. *Administrative Tribune*, 27(5), 146-152.
- Li, J., Hou, L., & Tang, L. (2021). Relationship between air quality and economic growth in key areas of air pollution control in China based on the Environmental Kuznets Curve. *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, 41(22), 8845-8859. <https://doi.org/10.5846/stxb202105121236>
- Li, L., Liang, X., & Li, J. (2024). China’s policy for the control of air pollution and air pollution control: An empirical research based on city-level panel data. *Ecological Economy*, 40(3), 179-186.
- Li, S., & Zhang, F. (2022). Environmental regulation and vertical integration: Empirical evidence from China. *Journal of Systems & Management*, 31(5), 931-940.
- Li, Z., Guo, S., Zhang, Z., Lin, H., Zhang, L., He, X., & Zheng, X. (2025). Chemical speciation of atmospheric intermediate volatility and semi-

volatile organic compounds on molecular level and the estimation of its contribution to secondary organic aerosol formation. *Acta Scientiae Circumstantiae*, 45(8), 32-45. <https://doi.org/10.13671/j.hjkxxb.2025.0095>

Liu, J., Li, Y., & Bai, X. (2020). Environmental regulations, spatial spillover effects, and urban environmental quality: Evidence from Guanzhong Area in China. *Journal of Catastrophology*, 35(4), 1-7.

Luo, Q., & Huang, W. (2024). Coordinating economic growth and environmental protection: From the perspective of the emissions abatement effect of the decline in trade policy uncertainty. *Finance & Trade Economics*, 45(3), 127-143. <https://doi.org/10.19795/j.cnki.cn11-1166/f.20240315.006>

Ma, X., Li, N., & Guo, C. (2023). A study of the policy effects on China's emissions trading system. *Ecological Economy*, 39(2), 188-200.

Meng, Q., & Wei, N. (2018). Structural obstruction, interest constraint and horizontal intergovernmental collaboration: the practice of intergovernmental horizontal collaboration of transboundary air pollution in Jing-Jin-Ji region. *Hebei Academic Journal*, 38(6), 8. [без DOI / требует уточнения]

Song, H., & Wang, Y. (2016). Legal countermeasure of air pollution prevention during the coordinated development of Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei. *China Population, Resources and Environment*, 26(S1), 75-78. [без DOI / требует уточнения]

Song, X., Shen, T., Zhao, C., Wang, C., & Sun, Q. (2021). Thoughts on the key directions of China's atmospheric pollution control in the next 15 years. *Environmental Protection*, 49(6), 43-47. <https://doi.org/10.14026/j.cnki.0253-9705.2021.06.011>

Su, J., Hu, J., & Li, Q. (2016). Study on the innovation and practice of tradable permits under the condition of market economy management — taking Inner Mongolia as an example. *Environmental Protection*, 44(1), 50-52. [без DOI / требует уточнения]

Suo, L. (2020). Strategic change in the region, policy regionalization and changes in the

structure of the collaborative governance organization for air pollution. *Journal of Tianjin Administration Institute*, 22(4), 55-68. <https://doi.org/10.16326/j.cnki.1008-7168.2020.04.007>

Sun, X., Bai, Y., & Wang, C. (2023). Synergistic effects of reduce pollution and carbon emissions: Policy barriers and innovation path. *Chinese Journal of Environmental Management*, 15(2), 16-23. <https://doi.org/10.16868/j.cnki.1674-6252.2023.02.016>

Sun, Y., & Zhou, C. (2022). The spatio-temporal evolution characteristics and influencing factors of collaborative governance of air pollution in the Yangtze River Delta region. *Geographical Research*, 41(10), 2742-2759. <https://doi.org/10.11821/dlyj020220294>

Wang, J. (2015). A research about the competitive effects of the air pollution regulation among local governments. *Journal of Guizhou University of Finance and Economics*, (06), 80-89. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1003-6636.2015.06.008>

Wang, L., Wang, L., & Zhang, W. (2022). Science and technology progress on air pollution prevention and control in recent ten years and future prospect in China. *Climatic and Environmental Research*, 27(6), 787-794. <https://doi.org/10.3878/j.issn.1006-9585.2022.22015>

Wang, S., Lv, L., & Luo, H. (2020). Study on China's climate change targets and strategies for the 14th Five-year Plan and the future. *Environmental Protection*, 48(20), 51-55. <https://doi.org/10.14026/j.cnki.0253-9705.2020.20.009>

Wang, S., Lv, L., & Sun, Q. (2024). Fifty years of Chinese-style environmental governance: From government negative incentive to multiple governance incentive compatibility. *Environmental Protection*, 52(Z1), 54-58. <https://doi.org/10.14026/j.cnki.0253-9705.2024.z1.015>

Wang, X., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Construction and development of China environmental policy system: from the perspective of ecological

civilization. *Journal of Shandong University of Finance and Economics*, 33(5), 43-50.

Wang, Y. (2020). Usage of policy tools for coordinated government control of air pollution: Policy text analysis based on three provinces and one city in the Yangtze River Delta region. *Jiangnan Tribune*, (04), 26-32.

Wu, X., Hu, Y., & Ning, C. (2025). The logic of intergovernmental non-coordination: Organizational structures, inter-actor relations, and cross-domain governance action strategies — An examination of the joint air pollution prevention and control mechanism in the Yangtze River Urban Agglomeration. *Journal of Public Management*, 1-30. <https://doi.org/10.16149/j.cnki.23-1523.20250818.001>

Wu, Y. (2023). Research on the countermeasures for the “Going Global” of China’s atmospheric environmental protection industry under the background of the “Belt and Road Initiative”. *Shanxi Chemical Industry*, 43(4), 268-270. <https://doi.org/10.16525/j.cnki.cn14-1109/tq.2023.04.098>

Xue, W., Xu, Y., Shi, X., & Lei, Y. (2021). Atmospheric environment management in China: progress and outlook. *Chinese Journal of Environmental Management*, 13(5), 52-60.

Ye, F., Yu, J., & Li, H. (2016). Research on some problems about main air pollutants emissions

trading. *Environmental Engineering*, 34(S1), 1076-1078.

Yu, Q., Duan, L., & Hao, J. (2021). Acid deposition in China: Sources, effects and control. *Acta Scientiae Circumstantiae*, 41(3), 731-746.

<https://doi.org/10.13671/j.hjkxxb.2020.0340>

Yu, Y., & Yin, L. (2022). The evolution of Chinese environmental regulation policy and its economic effects: A summary and prospect. *Reform*, (03), 114-130.

Zhang, P., Peng, B., Mi, Z., Lin, Z., & Du, H. (2025). Policy relevance and collaborative governance: Empirical analysis based on urban air policies. *Systems Engineering — Theory & Practice*, 45(1), 1-16.

Zhang, X., & Liu, X. (2025). How does the policy mix intensity affect policy effectiveness? A study based on air pollution control policy mix in China. *Journal of Public Administration*, 18(4), 118-137+199.

Zhu, Y., Xu, M., Li, H., Li, S., & Peng, S. (2021). A quantitative study on the policy of collaborative governance of air pollution after the implementation of the “Ten Atmospheric Regulations”. *Environmental Protection and Circular Economy*, 41(2), 96-100. <https://doi.org/10.3969/j.issn.1674-1021.2021.02.025>